

A MEAL THAT COUNTS! HOW PROPER FOOD EDUCATION CAN DECREASE FOOD WASTE IN SCHOOL CANTEENS

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Abstract

Objectives: The primary purpose of the research is to foster a positive relationship with food among students and, consequently, proper nutrition as a foundation for healthy life even in adulthood. According to UNESCO 2010, despite being the birthplace of the Mediterranean diet, Italy ranks as one of the top countries in the world with the highest rate of childhood obesity.

Another goal is to support positive emotions associated with a varied and balanced diet, developing a serene relationship with food: repeated and non-coercive exposure to different foods appears essential to accustom children to various flavours, increasing the likelihood of enjoyment and acceptance. According to a survey by the Ministry of the Environment, these actions are necessary to discourage food waste, which currently involves about one-third of dishes prepared daily for the school canteens.

Methodology: Various methodologies were employed to generate interest among students, actively involving them in a constructive learning process through interactive lessons and implementing a laboratory-style teaching approach by applying the scientific method. Specifically, the co-teaching methodology effectively explained the fundamentals of nutrition to students through an inductive process. Starting from a concrete experience, the teacher guides the student to acquire an experiential method oriented towards observing the surrounding reality.

Results: In general, it can be stated that the nutritional education sessions were successful in the experimental group, leading to a reduction in food waste during lunch, a subsequent increase in the sampling of vegetables, and an improvement in awareness regarding the consumption of a healthy snack during the school break.

Conclusions: The obtained result demonstrated that the starting hypotheses had been verified and confirmed.

Keywords: food choices, food waste, healthy eating, laboratory didactics, nutrition.

1 INTRODUCTION

In everyday life, Italy, the birthplace of the Mediterranean diet, recognized as a virtuous model of health and a UNESCO World Heritage for Humanity in 2010, clashes with a sad record: being among the countries with the highest childhood obesity rates (Nestlé, 2018). While nutrition is a fundamental need for the human species, healthy eating involves ensuring an adequate intake of calories and nutrients and their proper distribution throughout the day, ensuring optimal physical and cognitive development during the growth years (Landi, 2021). Italian data indicate that more than half of adults and approximately one in six children are overweight or obese (OECD, 2017). Numerous surveys suggest that in recent years, the population has been experiencing issues related to poor eating habits and unhealthy lifestyles: the current global paradox sees over a billion people overweight or even obese, in stark contrast to the analogous figure of those in conditions of difficult food survival (MIUR, 2015). Since 1990, there has been an alarming increase in overweight among youth: according to 2010 data from the "Okkio alla Salute" project, 22.9% of measured children were overweight, and 11.1% were obese (MIUR, 2011).

The lifestyle of technologically advanced societies, including Italy, is characterized by a progressive increase in sedentary behaviour. However, physical activity and movement are decreasing: our body's energy expenditure decreases while dietary consumption remains almost unchanged. The World Health Organization's "Childhood Obesity Surveillance Initiative" confirmed this data: a study conducted between 2015 and 2017 on over 300,000 primary school children (6-9 years old) revealed that the rate of childhood obesity in our country is 21% for males and 14% for females. This percentage reaches 42% and 38% when considering overweight boys and girls (Nestlé, 2018).

In this context, schools emerge as a critical setting for essential preventive action in food education aimed at younger generations (Zandonella Necca, 2014). While families traditionally transmitted the values of daily food consumption, in recent decades, schools have taken on more responsibility for these issues (MIUR, 2011), especially since just over half of Italian students consume 3 out of 5 meals in school cafeterias. MIUR guidelines from 2011 and 2015 for food education argue that it is essential to promote complex and systemic approaches to food education in schools, helping students understand the benefits of a healthy lifestyle and the food system. The new generations must contend daily with social transformation factors that strongly and often negatively influence eating behaviours and choices made at the table. Among these factors is the "deconstruction of meal preparation, manifested in the search for and consumption of easy-to-cook and ready-to-eat foods [...]; the deconstruction of the daily eating pattern and the spread of meals outside the home" (MIUR, 2015).

Adding to these challenges is a critical issue related to the school canteen: the "significant portion of food waste" (CREA, 2018). An investigation made by the Ministry of the Environment reveals that approximately one-third of prepared dishes are discarded in Italian school cafeterias. According to the Oricon Hearing (Collective Catering and Nutrition Observatory, 2017), 12.6% of meals go unconsumed daily. These data underscore the need for continued efforts to promote food education that not only helps children stay healthy but also prevents food waste for the well-being of the planet, allowing children to, in line with the goals of Agenda 2030, "understand the complexity of the world they live in and collaborate, speak, and act for positive change" (United Nations, 1948).

Introducing Life Sciences in primary school aims to expand the conventional perspective and understanding of scientific education in today's educational institutions. Typically, during the initial phase of education, Biology is often categorized under general Sciences, making it impractical to delve into all its facets given the limited hours allocated to this subject (Palmieri et al., 2019; Masiero et al., 2022). Nevertheless, offering students a holistic overview of this discipline is feasible. It is crucial to consider critical aspects of Science in general, such as redefining the concept of a "laboratory" in the classroom. Rather than being solely a space for manufacturing products, it should be viewed as an environment where students develop cognitive styles, understand their significance based on specific objectives, and where they can observe the world around them (Meneghetti et al., 2017).

A laboratory serves as a place where children can directly engage with the tangible reality, taking hands-on

actions and becoming motivated to cultivate their Critical Thinking (Tonon et al., 2013; Forlin et al., 2018). It involves highlighting strategies, categories, and structures of thought that guide the comprehension of phenomena using the scientific research method. It is particularly suited for primary school pupils requiring hands-on manipulation of content.

Another crucial element is acknowledging students' prior knowledge, considering it a foundational aspect of science education that facilitates the assimilation of new knowledge (Pavan & Santovito, 2014; Tura et al., 2018). By personally exploring and discovering natural events, children construct a knowledge network comprising reproducible experiences in a controlled environment, enabling them to reprocess learned concepts and expand their knowledge base.

These theories converge on the concept of an active teaching program for Science and Biology. Various approaches aim to achieve this objective, all rooted in lectures complemented by experimental activities, demonstrations, experiments, and investigations. Student participation is crucial, requiring them to actively observe and experience to enhance their understanding (Toninato & Santovito, 2015; Capparotto, 2017; Fassinato et al., 2018; Tonon et al., 2020). Consequently, active laboratory didactics have emerged as the most desirable method for teaching Science in primary schools.

Finally, adopting a "phenomenological approach" with students learning biology is essential. This involves using a "fact of reality," an event in the classroom that prompts students to reflect on the phenomena surrounding them (Gallina et al., 2019). This approach allows for a gradual introduction to scientific discovery through spontaneous and profound engagement, inherently implying a fundamental understanding of the world. Particularly in the early years of school, exploring the "small world" surrounding children in their daily lives is crucial for acquiring knowledge of the world (Grando et al., 2018a, 2018b; Lui et al., 2019).

2 METHODOLOGY

The experimental research was conducted between March and May 2023, totalling 10 hours, in two first-grade classes belonging to the comprehensive institute of Cassola (Vicenza, Italy): the experimental group consisted of 20 students from class 1C, and the control group comprised 22 students from class 1B. From a methodological standpoint, activities were presented playfully in the experimental group, using interactive lessons and a laboratory-based didactic approach where the scientific method was implemented. The co-teaching methodology in collaboration with a nutrition biologist and the application of experiential methods were crucial in placing the students in a genuine experiential situation, allowing them to acquire specific knowledge related to nutritional sciences.

The teaching project was developed in four steps, as depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. The teaching project

First step
Introduction to awareness about food waste generated by the school canteen.
Second step

The food pyramid: sensory experiences for understanding the foods it consists of.

smell with nose

taste with mouth.

touch with hands

Third step

The dish I would like and the healthy dish: why are there foods that should be consumed in reduced quantities?

educational game

healthy dish

Fourth step

Help me eat like this: healthy dishes to share!

3 RESULTS

The data collection was carried out biweekly for March and April. It involved two distinct moments: the first, after lunch in the cafeteria, consisted of weighing the amount of food left by the children on their trays with a scale for analyzing the daily food waste of the class. The quantitative measurement allowed the association of the menu with the waste, enabling the modification or replacement of disliked dishes in collaboration with the cafeteria. Once back in the classroom, the students were presented with a simple questionnaire, wholly anonymous and consisting of two multiple-choice questions:

1. How much did I eat?
2. How much did I like it?

Each food item presented in the cafeteria was assigned a different colour for each occasion, allowing the detection of consumed foods. For the second question, the children were offered three emojis (smiling, indifferent, sad), and only one could be coloured based on their liking of the tray presented.

For accurate data collection, the daily waste per child was investigated, as the children in the experimental group present during lunch, excluding any absences, were 14, while the students in the control group were 20.

The graph of Figure 1 shows a substantial decrease in discarded food per child in the experimental group: if, initially, it hovered around an average of 3.74%, after the nutritional education interventions, the value decreased to an average of 2.95%. On the other hand, the control group started with an average waste per student of 3.11%, and after the experimentation, this increased to an average of 3.31%.

Figure 2. Graph of waste per child

The obtained results are even more evident in Figure 2, where I analyzed the delta percentage. Initially, the experimental group consumed an average of 22% more than a child in the control group. The average value significantly decreased to 10.09% at the end of the proposed interventions.

Figure 2. The percentage delta for the experimental group

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In traditional teaching settings, knowledge is conveyed passively from teacher to student, with pupils following a deductive approach imposed by the teacher. The teacher supplies solutions and answers to problems; the textbook is a constant reference for all activities. This conventional method focuses on teaching, overshadowing the students' learning process (Gaiotto et al., 2013; Trevisan & Santovito, 2015; Rossi & Santovito, 2016; Barbacovi et al., 2018).

Conversely, laboratory didactics favours an inductive method, allowing students to independently discover regularities, rules, and constants in the given problems. Through discovery, students construct knowledge networks in social interaction with peers, connecting observed and studied phenomena to their experiences and daily lives. The student becomes the central figure in the learning process, while the teacher assumes the role of an indirect expert guide (Zanata & Santovito, 2020; Cazzador et al., 2022; De Rossi et al., 2022; Tonon et al., 2023).

Within this project, students exposed to the experimental method had the opportunity to engage within a scientific learning community. They discovered theoretical concepts, observed and manipulated them, and utilized specific instruments, fostering more profound and mature learning than the oral transmission of textbook concepts. Given the potential difficulty of biology concepts for younger students, an indirect approach through stories presenting characters and backgrounds related to biology was suggested. These stories, delivered particularly, stimulate imagination while imparting knowledge (Bolzon et al., 2022; Bertoncetto et al., 2023; Masiero et al., 2023; Massignani et al., 2023).

Experimental moments were integrated with reflection and discussion, turning the interaction and debate into essential teaching tools. These discussions aimed to transform the object of experience into a discourse that is negotiated, shared, and aligned with scientific principles, especially as students become more self-aware (Lago et al., 2017; Chiesa et al., 2019; Massarin et al., 2023; Pasquetto et al., 2023).

Efforts were also made to pique students' curiosity and motivation by establishing connections between their daily lives and the proposals of the experimental laboratory. These experiences aimed to lay a solid foundation for a lifelong, conscious approach to learning (Favaron et al., 2017; Corbolino et al., 2020; Gaiotto et al., 2020; Trevisan et al., 2023).

In conclusion, the significance of laboratory didactics employed in this research was demonstrated in

facilitating the transmission of experiences in various contexts and promoting meaningful learning in Life Sciences (Gaiotto & Santovito, 2016; Dal Pozzo et al., 2023; Rossi et al., 2023; Toninato et al., 2023). These results demonstrate the effectiveness of exposing children to nutritional education courses: they should unfold throughout their lives because the more incentive is consistent, integrated, and repeated, the more effective they are in activating and producing positive changes (Barzanò & Fossi, 2015). The acquired competence manifested in creating a small "Help Me Eat Like This" notebook for families. With this artefact, students should be able to explain and apply what they have learned in their daily contexts, becoming vehicles of knowledge because learning to eat well starts from a young age!

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